

Structural Features And Registration Of The World Brand Bursa Knife

Dünya Markası Bursa Bıçağının Yapısal Özelliği ve Tescili

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Özet

Bursa Bıçağının tam anlamıyla önemini yansıtan bu makale üç ana bölümden oluşmaktadır. Makalenin birinci bölümünde coğrafi işaret tescilinin tanımı, türleri, Tarihi Bursa Bıçağının tescil edildiği türü, yasal sorumlulukları ve önemi, Bursa bıçağının özellikleri, tescil kaynağı olan yerel özellikler yer almaktadır. İkinci bölümde 1953 tarihli ateşli silahlar, bıçaklar ve diğer aletler hakkındaki kanunun Bursa bıçağı, bıçak ve bunların üretimini nasıl etkilediği ve günümüz yaptırımları tartışılmıştır. Makalenin sonuç kısmında ise Tarihi Bursa Bıçağının marka değeri, oluşturulması gereken marka kişiliği ve satış politikaları ele alınmakta ve önerilerde bulunmaktadır. Ayrıca bu bölümde makale kapsamında elde edilen bulgular değerlendirilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bursa, bıçak, tescil, marka, üretim.

Abstract

This article that reflects its very sense importance of the Bursa Knife consists of three main parts: The first part of the article consists of the definition of geographical indication registration, its types, the type with which the Historical Bursa Knife is registered, the legal responsibilities and importance, the characteristics of the Bursa knife, the local characteristics that are the sources of the geographical indication registration, the purpose and scope of the article, and finally the material and the method. In the second part, how the 1953 law on firearms, knives and other tools affected the Bursa knives, knives in general and their production, and today's sanctions have been discussed. In the results part of the article, the brand value of the Historical Bursa Knife, the brand personality that needs to be created and the sales policies have been discussed and suggestions have been made. In addition in this part, the findings obtained within the scope of the article have been evaluated.

Keywords: Bursa, knife, registration, brand, production.

Introduction

Throughout the history, the cultures of nations, including the Turkish culture, have been enriched with traditional handicrafts and have acquired unique characteristics (Parlak, 2021: 161). The national culture, which is the nutrition supply of geographical indications, can directly affect production when it starts to carry the characteristics of the region. After all, the geographical indication is a protection method that is regulated by law and has the sanction power. Therefore, registration has local, regional and country generality. It does not confer the rights attributed to each citizen of the country to a particular person or group. Taking advantage of the registration rights and privileges means that the production is open to inspection and will meet the sanctions arising from the complaint. Moreover, product registration gives privilege to the product, not to the manufacturer. Even if indirectly, the protected product protects both the producer and the consumer, and keeps the cultural gains alive. Harari defines culture as 'the multiplicity of behavior

patterns' (2017:49), he also draws attention to the geographical influences. As a result, the vital diversity called culture cannot be thought of independently of the living area. In this context, the geographical indication emphasizes the direct contribution of a factor belonging to that geography at the production stage.

Geographical Indication and Its History

Geographical indication refers to the name of the local product, which owes its source of differentiation from its similarities to the region. In this sense, the geographical indication 'It is a sign indicating a product that is identified with the region, area, region or country of origin in terms of a distinctive feature, reputation or other characteristics.' (www.patent.gov.tr. E.T. 19.01.2019). In this manner, the registered historical Bursa knife lives in the traditional way of production.

The starting point of the geographical indication is 'The first legal regulations were made with the Paris Convention in 1883 and its scope was clarified with the Lisbon Agreement in 1958' (Suratno, 2004; 89, via Şahin). The edict, which was published in Bursa in 1502 with the name 'Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa', about 500 years before the application of the geographical indication protecting the product, is the first consumer law in history. 'Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa' (Bursa Municipality Law) is also the world's first standard law. This law came into effect with the order of Sultan Bayezid II (Özdemir, 2017:1). On the other hand, the first registration under the name of geographical indication in Turkey was made in 1871 under the name of 'Alameti Farika Nizamnamesi' (Trademark Regulations) (Akay, 2016: 369). The 'Trademark Regulations' took its current form in 1995 with the Decree Law No. 555. The application of 'Geographical Indications', as a commonly accepted global reference, was declared by the Turkish Patent Institute that is the official institution related to the registration rights (Şahin, 2013:25).

Benefits and Structural Properties of the Historical Bursa Knife

The knife, which belongs to the group of cutting and piercing weapons and tools, consists of a handle and a barrel (Piber, 2005: 12-13). In Bursa, the cutlery started with big varieties such as machete, attack sword, ax and Ottoman knife yatagan that vary from 60 centimeters (24 in) to 80 centimeters (31 in) in length and curved forward. Sarac explained the development of the knife with the expression 'After the Janissary, large kinds of cutting tools that got shorter and shorter were replaced by smaller wedges, pointed knives, and then bread, table and fruit knives' (Sarac, 2005:949). This long process was also the basis of the present structure of the historical Bursa knife. Two important events became the milestone for the Bursa knives and their masters. The first of these was the 93 War. Losing this war caused more than one million Ottoman citizens in the Balkans and the Caucasus to migrate to Anatolia as refugees. It can be said that especially the knife masters migrated and settled in Bursa and brought innovation and vitality to the Bursa knives by fusing their own culture with the Bursa culture.

The second important development for Bursa and Bursa cutlery was the firearms law no. 6136 enacted in 1953. Doğanay explained the effect of this law as 'Most of the Sürmene knife masters had to migrate to the cities such as İstanbul, Bursa and Kocaeli' (Doğanay, 2013:52). On the other hand, the law prohibited making and selling slotted, fluted knives and similar tools. In accordance with this law, all striated and grooved knives were seized with a report and cutlers were almost sentenced to starvation. Although the situation may seem unfortunate, the Bursa knife has taken advantage of these two historical events.

1. Immigrant knife masters, by making innovations in the ergonomic structure of the knife, saved the Bursa knife from the appearance of a weapon between a sword and a wedge. However, 'willow tongue, snake tongue, waist knife and knives called eared' (Kavaklı, 2007:65) it is still possible to see the characteristics of Turkish swords.
2. Bursa cutlery met a new folding knife like the Albanian pocket knife.
3. At the stage of quenching the blade, 'keep the chestnut charcoal
4. Immigrant masters' (Gülşen, interview: 13.04.2021) who met with the quenching process increased the sharpness of the barrel by making important improvements in the quenching process, and prevented blunting to a large extent by preventing deformations in the blade. By adding a third 'v' to a 'v' or double 'v' mouth, which came from the sword, wedge and dagger tradition, both the sharpness of the blade was increased and the Bursa knife was given an identity.

Picture 1. Immigrant knife masters who settled in Bursa after the 93 War added a third 'v' blade to the blade, increasing the sharpness of the blade.

1. With the law numbered 6136, striates and grooves were removed from the Bursa knife and the knife was left bare. This inconvenience enabled the masters to engrave their own signature on the knife steel and paved the way for branding. (Figure 2).
2. The Bursa knife has literally got rid of its weapon appearance.
3. The hard and iron-structured barrel resulting from the weapon's feature has left its place to a more flexible and sharp barrel. This flexibility has been so successful that it has come to define the knifemaker and the Bursa knife.

4. Bursa knife with flexible barrel has become light and functional, has gained structural terminology (Figure 2).

Picture 2. The Bursa knife, which got rid of the appearance of a weapon with the law numbered 6136, reached branding with the signatures of the masters on the knife steel, and terminological consciousness with its light, flexible steel and balanced handle structure.

1. With many new designs such as butcher, bread, cheese, fruit and hunting knives, classification in knives has started and each knifemaker has his own model. More than 150 knife models are produced today.
2. The understanding of knives production has changed, and remembrance and souvenir knives have begun to be produced. This new understanding started the tradition of decorating the handle and barrel of the knife. In addition, with this tradition, the tradition of knife sheath was abandoned and the application of sheath (packaging) began.
3. The mastery of the knife became even more perfect; the phrase 'the juice of the knife is the honor of the cutler' has become a kind of Hippocratic oath of Bursa cutlery.

While all these constitute the structural features of the Bursa knife, it is necessary to add mastery skills such as 'the barrel is straight where it meets the handle, there is no cutting error at the junction of the barrel and the handle' as Küçükata mentioned (Küçükata, Beştan, 2011).

Technical Specifications of the Historical Bursa Knife:

Defining the Bursa knife as being limited to its sharpness is insufficient for the 700-year-old Bursa knife. Sharpness is not a feature; it is functionality. Otherwise, the knife cannot be mentioned.

Steel is the most important building material of the blade. Therefore, the steel must be of good quality, durable and resistant to corrosion. The hardness feature is the feature that distinguishes the knife from the others and is shaped by the skill of the master. The hardness ratio increases the brittleness of the blade as well as making it strong. The hardness of blade steels is

determined by the Rockwell Hardness's C scale. This scale is defined as 'The Rockwell hardness value that measures the resistance of the metal against the applied pressure' (Kai:2021:7).

When the historical Bursa knife is evaluated technically:

1. **Its barrel is Solid:** T5 and T7 quality steel is used in the production of historical Bursa knives. Chestnut bark charcoal comes to the fore in the traditional method of heat process. In production with modern technology, the C scale of Rockwell Hardness, known as the heat treatment method, is used for hardness adjustment. In both methods, the steel hardness must be at least 52 HRC. While the hardness can be increased up to 56 HRC depending on the area of use of the produced blade, being below it can cause the steel to soften, premature deformation and decrease its sharpness. In heat treatments above 56 HRC, the tendency to breakage increases (TSE, Bursa knife registration report).
2. **Method of Quenching the Steel is Special:** This process is purely known as the master-skill. In production with the modern technology, the method used as a coolant process replaces the quenching process. The process of hardening and quenching the steel is one of the important distinguishing features to create the sharpness of the Bursa knife (TR, Bursa, Patent No: C2915/0004, 2018).
3. **Chestnut Wood or Bark Coal is Used in Heat Treatment:** Craftsmanship is important in the Bursa knives. Chestnut charcoal is used in the quenching process of Bursa knife (Erdal, 2016:8). The carbon content of chestnut charcoal is higher than other coal. Döşemen explained this process with the expression 'In the experimental studies, the chestnut bark, which has a high waste potential and obtained from the Bursa region, was used as a raw material source in the production of activated carbon' (Döşemen, 2009:29). The chestnut shell, which contains 35.66 percent carbon, is also used in the production of activated carbon. According to the results of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), 2 percent ash, 76 percent volatile matter and 22 percent fixed carbon content were identified especially in the chestnut shell. The low ash content allows it to heat up in a short time and stay in the embers for a long time. In her analyzes made, Döşemen explained that 'the activation temperature of the chestnut shell is 873 °K, the heating rate is 15 °K/min. and the waiting time is 45 min.' (Döşemen, 2009:29). In this analyzes, it was observed that the highest iodine number value (785 mg/g) was achieved with the raw material produced from the chestnut

Table 1. Elemental Analysis Results of Bursa Chestnut Shell (Source: Yasemin Döşemen, M. Sc. Thesis)

Elemental Analysis Results (Dry Base)	Chestnut bark
C (%)	35,66
H (%)	4,53
O (%)	53,63
N (%)	0,37
O/C	1,13
H/C	1,52
N/C	0,0009
S(%)	-
Empirical Formula	CH_{1,52}O₁₁₃N_{0,009}

shell with the largest surface area (1319 m²/g). This apparently increases the quality of Bursa Knife.

4. **Flexibility:** The flexibility of the steel is in the foreground in Bursa knife. Craftsmanship makes the steel hard, flexible and strong. In Japanese knives, while this process is done with high quality Aogami Blue Steel and ZDP-189 steel, this quality is achieved from lower quality French steels such as T5 and T7, entirely with the skill of Bursa masters.
5. **Knife Handles are Strong:** An obvious feature of Bursa Knife, which is produced with traditional or modern technology, is the strength of the handles. Because of this feature, the handles may not be considered elegant. Deer, buffalo, goat-locust and bone are used in knife handles. In addition, the most precious and rare trees are used as handles in the Bursa Knives. For example, a knife handle is made from the juniper wood, it always gives the smell of juniper (TR, Bursa, Patent No: C2915/0004, 2018., Erdal, 2018).

Purpose and Scope:

The purpose of this article is to guide the historical Bursa knife in post-registration production, sales and stamping of the knife. While the geographical features of the registered historical Bursa knife are revealed, it is also explained how the registration logo will be struck on the steel. Within the scope of the article, it is aimed to be a guide by researching how the 1953 law on firearms, knives and other tools affected the Bursa knife manufacturers and what responsibilities they imposed. It is aimed to increase the current brand value of the historical Bursa knife by increasing its value after registration, ensure the continuity of the production quality and prevent the producers or sellers who may seek unfair profits.

Material and Method

The article titled 'Bursa Brand in Knife and Knife' (Erdal, 2016) published in 2016 was the main source for the registration of the historical Bursa knife. With this article, the historical research of the Bursa knife was made and the features that made it famous were revealed. The handle, barrel and construction techniques of the Bursa knife were revealed by the quantitative research method and visualized with drawings. The Bursa knife masters were interviewed, photographs were taken and archived

Findings

In the historical Bursa Knife research, first of all, the features that made the knife Bursa were identified. The features of the Bursa knife are shown in pictures 1 and picture 2. The brand value of the Bursa knife has also been revealed in the findings. The definition of the brand, its importance, and the characteristics of the Bursa knife have all been extracted. This is explained under a separate title.

Brand Value of Historical Bursa Knife:

Brand can simply be defined as follows; It is everything that is known, recognized and separated from the like in some way. In order for something to be a brand, it must be known by at least one person; for it to be a good brand, it must be known by many and to be of good quality, it

must be recommended. The concept of brand can be academically defined as follows: 'It is defined as a sign that distinguishes a good or a service related to its protection from other goods and services, or a distinctive sign that provides absolute rights to the owner in terms of showing the source or quality of the goods and services' (Dursun, Akay, 2016:364).

Creating a brand identity for the historical Bursa knife with registered quality starts with creating a brand personality. Brand personalities are the characteristic recognition and selectivity perceptions similar to human personalities. Brand personalities are applied with five different scales as "sincere, exciting, expert, sophisticated and tough" (Borça, 2004:72). The historical bursa knife has the personality of an expert brand with its solid, sharp, rust-resistant and flexible steel barrel, and balanced and solid handle structure.

Use of Geographical Indications on the Historical Bursa Knife:

The application of the geographical indication registration logo of the historical Bursa knife to the knife steel according to certain rules is important in terms of production and sales discipline. Discipline creates a sense of control in the producer, continuity in the seller and trust in the consumer.

Picture 3. Green color product registration logo

**TARİHİ
BURSA BİÇAĞI**

Figure 4. Historical Bursa Knife Logotype

Figure 5. Calculation and application of the Geographical Registration logo according to the steel width. (Knife Master Fatih Adliğ)

The purpose of the registration logo is to facilitate the activities of informing and controlling the consumer that the product is traditional. Therefore, the geographical indication registration logo (Figure 3) should be used with the Historical Bursa Knife logotype. The logotype created with the Aisle Seats JNL by Jeff Levine font (Figure 4) should be used to the right of the registration logo (Figure 5). The date should be written in Arial Black font on the left top of the logotype.

The supervisory board explains some rules in order to provide a standard in the application of the origin registration logo on the steel. Therefore, the historical Bursa knife registration logo should be applied to the outside of the knife, 0.5 cm from the knife handle and 0.3 cm from the steel back (upper part). The logo and logotype cannot be changed in any way and cannot be interpreted outside of standard usage. The logo size is calculated by adding 1 cm to the steel width in cm, according to the widest side of the blade steel (Figure 4). For example, the formula for calculating the logo size of a knife with a steel width of 3.5 cm; $3.5 \text{ cm} + 1 \text{ cm} = 4.5 \text{ cm}$ should be the length measurement of the logo. The height of the logo is determined by the automatic adjustment of the computer program. This sizing system is important for determining the logo size according to each size of the historical Bursa knife, which has more than 150 types of blades. However, in the TSE's geographical indication emblem user manual, there is a statement that it cannot be used for geographical indication emblems with a diameter smaller than 15 mm. It is not possible to use this size logo on fruit, breakfast, pocketknife or special knives with a steel width of 1 cm. Although the logo to be used on the steel of such knives was deemed appropriate to be applied according to the formula above, it was explained that a logo with a diameter of 15 mm should be used on the sheath or packaging of the knife. (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The rule that the diameter of the registration logo cannot be more than 15 mm may not be applicable to knife steel in some cases. In this case, the geographical logo with a diameter of 15 mm must be applied on the knife packaging. (Bıçak, Fatih Adliğ)

Results

There is no doubt that the Bursa knife, which has survived for 700 years, is still in existence today. However, in the face of developing technology, contract or pirate production, the struggle of a few veteran knife masters may not be enough for the Bursa knife to continue its existence. However, in order to keep the historical Bursa knife alive, it must carry its existence outside its geographical or home-country borders. The geographical registration obtained in line with this requirement is important in terms of showing that the historical Bursa knife is ready for the new steps to be taken for it. When the first historical Bursa knife international symposium is added to these important

steps such as the first knife design competition, the first knife museum, and the first geographical registration, it will have made its presence known in the international scientific world. In this direction, it is planned to establish a 'Bursa Knife and Cutting Tools Research Center' within the body of Bursa Uludağ University.

History of the Bursa knife is enough of proof that it is crucially important in its branding. With the dramatic unfortunate events that happened to the city with the 93 War and the 53 law, Bursa experienced troubled times in terms of both employment and knife production, and are still remembered as the years when knife production came to a standstill. On the other hand, the historical Bursa knife has managed to stand up by getting stronger. The role of immigrants in this resurrection was great and crucially important. Bursa knife of the present day was created, in which the innovations they brought and the experiences of Bursa knife masters were blended extremely well. The new era, which started with the prohibition of striates and grooves on knife steel with the 1953 law, put the Bursa knives in a difficult situation as well as all the knife manufacturers in the country. As they could not produce and sell them, also the late payment of the knives collected by the state brought the knife masters to the point of bankruptcy. However, even in this case, the Bursa cutlery succeeded in renewing itself and managed to create its own brand. So much so that the typology of Bursa knives was rearranged, and more functional and aesthetic knives were produced. This resurgence, which continued until the 1990s, started to stagnate again with the widespread use of fabrication and automation systems.

The fact that the historical Bursa knife has been registered is important for this and similar fluctuations. The center, which is planned to be opened within the university, will bring Bursa knives and knife masters to the academic environment and ensure that they are documented.

The quality will never degenerate, as the production and inspection of knives according to the conditions governed by the registration document will introduce a production standard. The geographical indication logo engraved on the steel of the knife and the signature of the master will be the assurance of this quality. Like the 'quenching the steel' method, which is accepted as the Hippocratic Oath of Bursa knives, the geographical registration logo that will be engraved on the knife will be a kind of Hippocratic Oath of quality and trust.

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Geniş Özet

Türk Patent Marka Kurumuna göre coğrafi işaret; benzerlerinden farklılaşmış ve bu farkı kaynaklandığı yöreye borçlu olan yöresel ürün adını ifade eder. Bu anlamda coğrafi işaret, belirgin bir niteliği, ünü veya diğer özellikleri bakımından kökenin bulunduğu yöre, alan, bölge veya ülke ile özdeşleşmiş bir ürünü gösteren işarettir. Coğrafi işaretler, ürünü sadece yöresel farklılığına göre değil, aynı zamanda geleneksel üretim birliğinin korunmasına da dikkat eder. Bu anlamda o ürünün, yöre üreticilerince aynı yöntem, teknik ve malzeme ile üretilmesini denetleyerek, kolektif bir koruma sağlar.

Bu çalışma ile tarihi Bursa bıçağının coğrafi işaret tescil süreç aşamaları anlatılırken, bu tescilin Bursa bıçağına ne kazandırdığı, üreticilerine hangi hak ve sorumluluklar getirdiği, yaptırımları ve geleceğe yönelik kazançları konu edilmiştir. Tescilli tarihi Bursa bıçağının, marka değeri, marka kişiliği, üretim aşamaları, yapısal ve teknik özellikleri, kullanılan çeliğin özellikleri, Bursa yöresinde yetişen kestane ağacı kömürü ve özellikleri gibi teknik ve akademik bulguların yanında gelenekselliğinin yaşatılmasına dair örnekler incelenmiştir.

Tarihten bu yana Türk kültürü dahil ulusların kültürü geleneksel el sanatlarıyla zenginleşmiş ve kendilerine has özellikler edinmiştir. Coğrafi işaretlerin besin kaynağını oluşturan ulusal kültür, bölgenin özelliklerini taşımaya başladığında, üretimi doğrudan etkileyebilmektedir. Nihayetinde coğrafi işaret, kanunla düzenlenmiş ve yaptırım gücüne sahip bir koruma yöntemidir. Çünkü tescil, yöresel, bölgesel ve ülke genelliğine sahiptir. Ülkenin her bir vatandaşına atfedilen hakları, belli bir kişiye veya zümreye vermez. Tescil hak ve ayrıcalıklarından yararlanmak, üretiminin denetime açık olduğunu ve şikâyet kaynaklı yaptırımların karşılayacağı anlamına gelir. Kaldı ki ürün tescilli üreticiye değil, ürüne ayrıcalık tanımaktadır. Dolaylı da olsa koruma altındaki ürün hem üreticiyi hem tüketiciyi koruyarak kültürel kazanımları yaşatır. Harrari, kültürü “davranış örüntülerinin çokluğu olarak tanımlarken, coğrafi etkilere de dikkat çekiyor. Neticesinde kültür denilen yaşamsal çeşitlilik, yaşam bölgesinden bağımsız düşünülemez. Bu bağlamda coğrafi işaret, üretim aşamasında, o coğrafyaya ait bir etkenin doğrudan katkısını vurgular.

Coğrafi işaret uygulaması 1883 yılında Paris Sözleşmesi ile ilk yasal düzenlemeler yapılmış 1958’de de Lizbon Anlaşması ile kapsamı netleştirilmiştir. Ürünü koruyan coğrafi işaret uygulamasından yaklaşık 500 yıl önce Bursa’da Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa” ismiyle 1502 yılında yayınlanan ferman, tarihte yapılan ilk tüketici kanunu olma özelliği taşır. Kanunnâme-i İhtisab-ı Bursa (Bursa Belediyesi Kanunu) ayrıca dünyanın ilk standart kanunudur. Bu kanun Sultan II. Bayezid emriyle yürürlüğe girmiştir. Buna karşın Türkiye’de coğrafi işaret adı altında ilk tescilleme, “Alameti Farika Nizamnamesi” ismiyle 1871 yılında yapılmıştır. Alameti Farika, günümüzdeki şeklini 1995 yılında 555 sayılı Kanun Hükmünde Kararname ile almıştır. Bilinen adıyla “Coğrafi İşaretler” uygulaması, Türk Patent Enstitüsü tescil haklarıyla ilgili resmi kurum olarak belirtilmiştir.

Tarihi Bursa Bıçağının aldığı coğrafi işaret tescili, el işçiliğine dayalı geleneksel üretim faaliyetinin, günümüz teknolojisine dayalı fabrikasyon üretime yenik düşmemesi, 700 yıllık geçmişine dayalı şöhretini ve ekonomik değerini kaybetmemesi adına önemlidir. Bu anlamda bu makale üç bölümden oluşmaktadır. Makalenin ilk bölümünü coğrafi işaret tescilinin tanımı, türleri, Tarihi Bursa Bıçağının hangi türle tescillendiği, yasal sorumluluklar ve önemi, Bursa bıçağının özellikleri, coğrafi işaret tesciline kaynaklık eden yöresel özellikler, makalenin amaç ve kapsamı, materyal ve metot oluşturmaktadır. İkinci bölümünde 1953 yılı ateşli silahlar ve bıçaklar ile diğer aletler hakkında kanunun Bursa bıçağını, bıçakçıları ve üretimini nasıl etkilediği, günümüzdeki yaptırımları konu edilmiştir. Makalenin son kısmında ise Tarihi Bursa Bıçağının marka değeri, oluşturulması gereken marka kişiliği ve satış politikaları ele alınarak önerilerde bulunulmuştur. Kalitesi tescilli tarihi Bursa bıçağı için marka kimliği yaratmak, marka kişiliği oluşturmakla başlar. Çünkü marka kişilikleri, insan kişiliklerine benzeyen karakteristik tanınırlık ve seçilirlik algılarıdır. Marka kişilikleri, samimi, heyecanlı, uzman, sofistike ve sert olmak üzere beş farklı skala ile uygulanırlar. Tarihi bursa bıçağı, sağlam, keskin, paslanmaya dayanıklı ve esnek çelikten oluşan namlusu ile dengeli ve sağlam sap yapısı ile uzman marka kişiliğine sahiptir.

700 yıldır varlığını sürdürebilmiş Bursa bıçağının, bundan sonra da bir şekilde var olabileceğinden şüphe edilmeyebilir. Ancak gelişen teknoloji, fason veya korsan üretim karşısında, birkaç emektar bıçak ustasının fedakarlığından öteye gidemeyebilir. Oysaki tarihi Bursa bıçağının yaşatılması için kendi coğrafi veya ülke sınırları dışına taşınması gereklidir. Bu gereklilik doğrultusunda alınan coğrafi tescil, tarihi Bursa bıçağının yeni atılacak adımlara hazır olduğunu göstermesi açısından önemlidir. İlk bıçak tasarım yarışması, ilk bıçak müzesi, ilk coğrafi tescilin alınması gibi önemli adımlara, yine ilk tarihi Bursa bıçağı uluslararası sempozyumunu da eklendiğinde, uluslararası bilim dünyasında da varlığından söz ettirmiş olacaktır. Bu doğrultuda Bursa Uludağ Üniversitesi bünyesinde “Bursa Bıçak ve Kesici Aletler Araştırma Merkezi” kurulması planlanmaktadır.

Bursa bıçağının tarihsel süreci, onun markalaşmasında ne derece önemli olduğunun kanıtı gibidir. 93 Harbi ve 53 yasası ile iki kez göç alan Bursa hem istihdam hem de bıçak üretimi olarak sıkıntılı günler yaşamışken, bıçak üretiminin durma noktasına geldiği yıllar olarak hatırlanmaktadır. Buna karşın tarihi Bursa bıçağı, daha da güçlenerek ayağa kalmayı başarmıştır. Bu dirilişte göçmenlerin payı büyük ve önemlidir. Onların getirdikleri yenilikler ile Bursalı bıçak ustalarının tecrübelerinin son derece iyi harmanlandığı bugünkü Bursa bıçağı yaratılmıştır. 1953 yasası ile bıçak çeliğine açılan yiv ve olukların yasaklanmasıyla başlayan yeni dönem, ülkenin tüm bıçak üreticilerinde olduğu gibi Bursa bıçakçıları da zora sokmuştur. Üretim ve satış yapamadıkları gibi devletin topladığı bıçaklara ödemeyi geç yapması, bıçak ustalarını iflas noktasına getirmiştir. Ancak bu durumda dahi Bursa bıçakçılığı kendini yenilemeyi başarmış ve markasını oluşturabilmiştir. Öyle ki Bursa bıçaklarının tipolojisi yeniden düzenlenmiş, daha işlevsel ve estetik bıçak üretimleri yapılmıştır. 1990'lara kadar devam eden bu diriliş, fabrikasyon ve otomasyon sistemlerinin yaygınlaşması ile yeniden durağanlaşmaya başlamıştır.

Tescil belgesinin hükmettiği şartlara göre bıçak üretiminin yapılması, denetlenmesi üretim standardı getireceği için kalite hiçbir zaman düşürülmemiş olacaktır. Bıçağın çeliğine kazanmış olan coğrafi işaret logosu ile ustanın imzası, bu kalitenin güvencesi olacaktır. Bursa bıçakçılarının bir tür Hipokrat'ı kabul edilen "çeliğe su verme" yöntemi gibi bıçağa kazanacak olan coğrafi tescil logosu da kalitenin, güvenin ve Bursa markasının Hipokrat'ı olacaktır.

Araştırmacıların Katkı Oranı Beyanı / Researchers' Contribution Rate Statement

Birinci Yazar (First Author) %60,
İkinci Yazar (Second Author) %40,

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Yayın Etiği Beyanı / Publication Ethics Statement

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